

Open Education in European Institutions of Higher Education - Survey 2026

INTRODUCTION

Welcome to the 2026 SPARC Europe survey on Open Education (OE).

Why take it?

We use your responses to shape future support and policy for Open Education for Europe. Your input is valuable whether your institution is already active or just exploring OE.

How to participate

Most respondents complete this survey in 10-15 minutes. You'll only see questions relevant to you.

A PDF version is available [here](#).

Deadline: **20 July 2026, 18:00 CEST**.

Only questions marked * are required.

You may share this survey with colleagues or submit multiple responses from different departments.

No personal details are required unless you wish to be notified of survey results. Responses are anonymised, reported in aggregate, then shared on Zenodo under a CC0 licence.

For questions, contact: survey@sparceurope.org. [Ethics and data policies](#) are available online.

By clicking "Next," you confirm your consent to participate.

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ABOUT YOU AND YOUR ORGANISATION

* 1. Which of the following best describes your organisation?

Please select one answer

- University / Comprehensive institution (e.g. covering all or most academic disciplines)
- University of Applied Sciences (college-type or professional education institution which does not award PhDs, or does so in only a few disciplines)
- Technical university / University of technology
- Distance learning university
- Specialised institution (e.g. medical science, music and arts school)
- Teaching college
- Other (please specify)

* 2. In what country is your organisation based?

* 3. What is the name of your organisation?

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Please note - we use this information to help identify any duplicate responses.

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ABOUT YOU AND YOUR ORGANISATION

This survey asks a range of questions about Open Education, and specifically Open Educational Resources (OER), and Open Educational Practices (OEP).

4. How long have you been involved in Open Education (OE)?

Please select one answer

- less than 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 3-5 years
- 6-10 years
- more than 10 years
- I am not involved in OE

5. What is your role within your organisation?

6. In which department is your role based?

Please select all that apply

- Library
- Education and Teaching services
- Technology and Information Services
- Faculty
- Policy Office
- Other (please specify)

7. Which departments, other than your own, are involved in OE in your institution?

Please select all that apply

- Library
- Education and Teaching services
- Technology and Information Services
- Faculty
- Policy Office
- Other (please specify)

- None of the above

8. What role does your department take in OE in your organisation?

Please select one answer

- A lead role
- A supporting role
- We are still deciding
- We do not have a role
- Other (please specify)

BUILDING CAPACITY

This section focuses on understanding roles and capacity at your organisation in relation to OE/OER.

* 9. What Open Education services do you provide?

Please select all that apply

- Advice on copyright and open licensing
- Collection management / dealing with education publishers and aggregators
- Course pack provision
- Creation of open textbooks
- Data curation & interoperability
- Discovery services
- Information literacy
- Knowledge exchange
- OER co-creation
- OER provision (evaluation, selection, etc) to complement courses
- Management & storage service (e.g. repositories)
- Metadata to index digital resources
- Participatory design
- Training / Education
- Other (please specify)

- None of the above

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BUILDING CAPACITY

10. Please describe the services, and which departments are involved in providing them and advocating for OE.

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11. What level of skills does your department have in these areas?

Please select one option per row

	A full set	Many	Limited	None	Don't know
Advice on copyright and open licensing	<input type="radio"/>				
Collection management / dealing with education publishers and aggregators	<input type="radio"/>				
Course pack provision	<input type="radio"/>				
Creation of open textbooks	<input type="radio"/>				
Data curation & interoperability	<input type="radio"/>				
Discovery services	<input type="radio"/>				
Information literacy	<input type="radio"/>				
Knowledge exchange	<input type="radio"/>				
OER co-creation	<input type="radio"/>				
OER provision (evaluation, selection, etc) to complement courses	<input type="radio"/>				
Management & storage service (e.g. repositories)	<input type="radio"/>				
Metadata to index digital resources	<input type="radio"/>				
Participatory design	<input type="radio"/>				
Training / Education	<input type="radio"/>				
[Insert text from Other]	<input type="radio"/>				

12. For areas where skills are limited or absent, what are the main reasons?

Please select all that apply

- Lack of staff
- Lack of training
- Not a current priority
- Skills provided elsewhere in the organisation
- Outsourced externally
- Other (please specify)

- None of the above

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DEVELOPING SUPPORTIVE POLICY

We would like to understand your OE policies in this section. We refer to policy as any formal document (e.g. strategy, roadmap, guidelines, white papers, roadmaps, declarations, and funding programmes) that supports OE , including OER and OEP, for an institution.

* 13. Does your organisation have a policy that addresses OE in any way?

Please select one answer

- Yes
- Under development
- Under consideration
- No
- I don't know

If yes, please add link here:

14. If you have a policy but it is not available via a link, please upload it here

Max size 16MB

Choose File

Choose File

No file chosen

DEVELOPING SUPPORTIVE POLICY

15. Is your organisation's OE policy part of a larger, overarching internal policy, or is it a standalone policy dedicated to OE?

Please select one answer

- Standalone policy dedicated to Open Education
- Part of a larger, overarching Open Science policy
- Part of different larger, overarching policy
- Other (please specify)

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DEVELOPING SUPPORTIVE POLICY

* 16. Does your organisation have a formal task force, committee or other entity with an Open Education focus?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

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DEVELOPING SUPPORTIVE POLICY

17. At what level in the organisation is the task force?

Please select all that apply

- Institutional level
- Library level
- Departmental level
- Other (please specify)

18. Which departments are involved in the task force or committee?

Please select all that apply

- Library
- Education and Teaching Support Services
- Technology and Information Services
- Faculty
- Policy Office
- Other (please specify)

19. Is the task force solely focused on Open Education or does it have a broader remit?

Please select one answer

- Yes - it is solely focused on Open Education
- No - it has a focus on issues beyond Open Education
- No - it has a focus on a range of Open Science activities, including Open Education
- Other (please specify)

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SUSTAINING OE, OER & OEP

20. How many FTE (full time equivalent) staff members are dedicated to working on OE in your department/library?

Please do not include work on Open Access, Open Scholarship or Open Science. We will ask about connections to these areas later in the survey.

If you cannot give a precise answer, please provide a reasonable estimate.

Please select one answer

- 0
- Less than 1
- 1-5
- 6-9
- 10 or more
- Don't know

21. Does your organisation have a grant programme or seed funding that supports the creation, search, reuse, repurpose, and adaptation of OER and their use in didactic activities as part of OEP?

This might be a programme dedicated to OE work or a broader scheme supporting educational innovation and / or excellence.

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

If yes, please provide the name of this programme or project and preferably a link to more information

22. From which budget or budgets does funding for OE come?

Please select all that apply

- Library budget
- Other institutional budget
- A national or regional project or programme
- A European project
- Other (please specify; For example: partnering with other institutions, joining a European University Alliance, etc.)

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REWARD & RECOGNITION

* 23. Are OE, OER and/or OEP rewarded or recognised in your organisation, whether formally or informally?

Please select one answer

- Yes
- We are considering it
- No
- Other (please specify)

- Don't know

REWARD & RECOGNITION

24. What recognition and reward mechanisms does your organisation use to promote OE, OER and / or OEP?

Please select all that apply

- Promotion or career progression criteria
- Internal grants or funding
- Awards or prizes
- Workload allocation
- Informal recognition
- Other (please specify)

- None of the above

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REWARD & RECOGNITION

25. How are reward mechanisms for OE related to other reward mechanisms in your institution?

Please select all that apply

- Dedicated mechanisms for Open Education
- Part of broader Open Science mechanism
- Part of broader Education mechanism
- Other (please specify)

- None of the above

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BENEFITS, CHALLENGES & AWARENESS RAISING

26. What are the major benefits you have identified from supporting Open Education in your organisation?

Please specify up to three

Benefit 1

Benefit 2

Benefit 3

27. What are the major challenges that you have in supporting Open Education in your organisation?

Please specify up to three

Challenge 1

Challenge 2

Challenge 3

28. We are particularly keen to understand the ways in which organisations raise awareness of the value of OE.

Please outline the ways in which you raise awareness of the value of OE, OER, and OEP in your organisation.

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CONNECTING OPEN EDUCATION & OPEN SCIENCE

* 29. We are interested in understanding how Open Education is connected to other open approaches in different institutions, through our [Connecting The Opens](#) programme.

To what extent are Open Education and Open Science connected in your organisation's strategy, policy or practice?

Please select one answer

- Through a shared/aligned institutional approach
- In some areas, but not in a coordinated way
- Mostly separate
- Not at all connected
- We do not currently work substantially in one or both of these areas
- Other (please specify)

CONNECTING OPEN EDUCATION & OPEN SCIENCE

30. In which areas, if any, do you see the strongest connection between Open Education and Open Science in your organisation?

Please select up to three answers.

- Institutional strategy or policy
- Staff roles, services and/or support structures
- Skills development and/or training
- Teaching and/or learning practices
- Research dissemination and/or communication
- Reward, recognition and/or incentive structures
- Equity, inclusion and/or access to knowledge
- Partnerships, networks and/or collaborative projects
- Other (please specify)

- None of the above

31. How much would the following help your organisation strengthen the connection between Open Education and Open Science?

	Extremely	Moderately	Slightly	Not at all
A clearer institutional policy / strategy or stronger leadership support	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Better alignment across departments or services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More funding or dedicated resources	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More guidance, examples or evidence of benefit and value	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Better recognition and reward mechanisms	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More staff or dedicated roles to support this work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More staff development or training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More opportunities for collaboration internally	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
More opportunities for collaboration externally	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other (please specify)

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ADDITIONAL COMMENTS

32. If you would like to add any further details to your survey response, please include these below.

Open text

* 33. We would like to contact respondents with the survey results and to involve you in Open Education activities and future surveys. Do you consent to being contacted for these purposes?

Your answer to this question has no impact on your survey response.

Yes

No

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YOUR DETAILS

34. Please provide your contact details so we can share the results of this survey and to inform you of future Open Education activities and surveys.

Name and surname

Email Address

35. Would you be willing for us to contact you to answer questions on the following topics?

Please select all that apply

- Different definitions and interpretations of OE, OER & OEP
- Communicating the importance of OE, OER & OEP
- Mechanisms that reward & recognise OE contributions
- Connecting Open Education and Open Science
- Promoting diversity, equity and inclusion in OE programmes
- Recognition and reward of OE, OER & OEP

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END OF SURVEY

Thank you very much for taking this survey.